

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ABILITIES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The role of creative ability in the formation of children's worldview is invaluable. Children's artistic taste is formed through their creative abilities. After all, the process of formation of imagination and concepts in a child starts from the preschool educational institution, and this period is the most important stage in terms of the content of the formation of the worldview. That is why preschool age is the main period in the formation of concepts and ideas.

Creativity is more important than knowledge.

Creativity is the door to possibilities

A. Eynshteyn

Today, our society needs intelligent and creative specialists more than ever. Today, creativity is one of the most important issues to be solved. Because as a creative, responsible for his work, a specialist who approaches the situation creatively, he contributes to the development of science, education, spirituality, enlightenment, technology, production, let's say in all areas. Therefore, it is urgent and important to start developing creative abilities from preschool educational institutions.

The task of pedagogues in pre-school educational organizations is to help the child organize daily activities that are considered the basis for the manifestation of life competencies and creative self-expression. It is important for educators to show the child the actions that should be taken every day to demonstrate his abilities.

MAIN PART

A creative product is an active product of the human mind. Today, it has been proven that preschool children can develop and develop creative activities in drawing, making clay and plasticine toys. In the process of education, due to listening to fairy tales and seeing various pictures, the child gradually begins to imagine things that are not included in the range of objects that he directly perceives before making a toy. At first, under the verbal influence of adults, voluntary images of imagination are formed in the child, and later they lead to the child's independent thinking.

Creativity is a person's ability to make creative decisions, understand, accept and create radically new ideas.

According to the teacher's instructions (make it yourself, think of something, find it, change it, etc.), children work together with the teacher and create creativity.

show their elements.

In the modern world, a person's creative abilities should be recognized as the most important part of his intelligence. Cultural values accumulated by mankind are the result of creative activity of people.

The creative potential of the young generation will determine the level of development of human society in the future. Educators should not forget that imitation is the main mechanism of formation of creativity. This means that in order to develop the child's creative abilities, among the people close to him, the child should be a creative person who identifies himself. Not only parents (or one of the parents), but also other adults (teachers, family friends, etc.) can act as a model of creative behavior for the child. It is especially effective if parents are "ideal heroes" with more creative features for children. In fact, "Creativity" is the individual qualities of a person that determine the success of various types of creative activity. Activities for the development of creative abilities of preschool children play an important role in the formation of a child's personality. All the studies conducted by scientists and psychologists in this field prove that children with creative abilities have a more stable spirit, communicate with them and have a friendly relationship. At a young age, it is recommended to pay special attention to comprehensive development, that is, to the development of literary, artistic and musical abilities of preschool children. Creativity is a combination of many qualities. Psychologists believe that the components of creativity are:

1. The ability to see the problem where others do not.
2. The ability to collapse mental operations, replace several concepts with one, and use symbols that have more and more capacity in terms of information.
3. The ability to use the skills acquired in solving one problem in solving another problem.
4. The ability to perceive reality as a whole, without dividing it into parts.
5. Ability to easily connect long concepts.
6. Memory's ability to provide the right information at the right time.
7. Show flexibility of thinking.
8. Ease of generating ideas.
9. Ability to create new non-standard ideas, develop creative thinking.
10. The ability to improve your "product" of your activity.
11. The ability to express different opinions.
12. Ability to refine details to improve the original idea.

When talking about the formation of abilities, it is necessary to dwell on the question of what age children's creative abilities should be developed. Psychologists have an assumption that creative abilities should be developed from a very early age. This hypothesis finds its confirmation in physiology. A child's brain grows especially quickly and "ripens" in the first years of life. This maturity, i.e., the growth of the number of brain cells and the anatomical connections between them, depends on the diversity and intensity of the work of the existing structures, as well as the extent to which the environment encourages the formation of new ones. From a psychological point of view, preschool age is a favorable period for the development of creative abilities, because at this age children are very inquisitive, they have a

great desire to learn about the world around them. The basis for the development of children's creative abilities is, first of all, freedom.

Parents should not force the child. Success in this regard requires patience and certain tactics - the parent should listen to the child's opinion, encourage his interest in any creative activity. Parents and guardians contribute to expanding children's experiences by stimulating curiosity, educating them, and involving them in various activities. Accumulation of experience and knowledge is a prerequisite for future creative activity. In addition, the thinking of preschool children is much freer than that of older children. For children to show creativity, they need to combine all these characteristics. As we know, preschool education organizations organize various activities to develop children's creativity and direct children to creative thinking. Based on this knowledge, preschool children should have the following skills. After completing educational activities in the field of "creativity", a 6-7-year-old child:

- shows interest in art and culture;
- values national traditions and perceives them as a part of everyday life;
- independently expresses his preference for a certain type of art;
- uses acquired knowledge and skills to create and implement creative plans in various life situations;
- understands the role of human creativity in changing the world.

A child's creativity can be developed not only in special classes.

Perhaps the game, which is the main activity of preschool children, is of great importance for the development of children's imagination. . It is best to develop creative abilities through play. It is in play that the child takes the first steps of creative activity. Adults should not only watch children's play, but also manage its development, enrich it, and introduce creative elements into the game. In addition, there are special games that can be played with children in their free time to develop creative skills. Interesting educational games developed by scientists are a clear proof of this. Another bright source of developing a child's imagination and creative thinking is a fairy tale. There are many storytelling techniques that educators can use to develop children's imaginations.

CONCLUSION

In the era of globalization, in the period of development of innovative techniques and technologies, the scope of thinking of children and their creative abilities are also expanding. A number of new programs are being introduced to develop children's creative abilities and thinking. Including: Mental Arithmetic is a program that develops art and intelligence. With the help of this program, children not only succeed in their studies, but also gain life motivation and expand their creative abilities. The mnemonic method is also a program that develops quick memory and the speed of creative thinking. Modern parents and teachers set themselves the task of creative development of the child. Great attention is paid to the development of such abilities. Therefore, it is often considered an important process to use TRIZ in educational programs for children of preschool age and to organize activities based on this process. Games and tasks based on this system help to develop active creative thinking, and also make the process of forming a creative personality more exciting for children and adults. From all of the above, we can conclude that preschool age provides excellent opportunities for the development of creative abilities. After analyzing different points of view

on the issue of the components of creative abilities, we can conclude that despite the difference in approaches to their definition, researchers unanimously distinguish the quality of creative imagination and creative thinking as important components of creative abilities.

Based on this, it is possible to determine the main directions for the development of children's creative abilities.

- development of imagination;
- development of thinking qualities that shape creativity.

One of the important reasons for the creative development of children is to create favorable conditions for the formation of their creative abilities.

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